

A qualitative synthesis of children's experiences with technology-assisted cognitive behavioural therapy (CBT)

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Review question

What are the overall themes in the experiences of school-aged children that have used different versions of technology-assisted cognitive behavioural therapy (CBT) for any mental or physical difficulties?

Searches

The following databases will be used searched:

? PsycINFO

? ACM Digital Library

? PubMed

? Embase

? JMIR

The search strategy will apply the database-specific methods of using the following search terms: (cognitive OR cognitive therapy OR CBT OR cCBT OR e-therapy OR web-assisted OR tech-assisted OR game-based OR internet) AND (child OR adolescent OR youth OR young people OR young person OR kid OR teen) AND (experience OR perspective OR view OR opinion OR feedback OR interview OR thought OR focus group OR qualitative).

Additionally, of the selected studies, reference sections will be hand-searched for any overlooked literature.

Types of study to be included

? Studies that are exclusively qualitative by design

? Studies that have a significant qualitative component alongside quantitative measures ? Formal qualitative studies of established or emerging technologies that has applied, or seeks to apply, computerised cognitive behavioural therapy

Condition or domain being studied

Thoughts, (user) experiences, reflections, feedback, and perspectives of school-aged children that have used technology-assisted CBT.

Participants/population

Inclusion Criteria:

- School-aged children under the age of 18 and over the age of preschool (age 6)
- Use of any form of technology-assisted CBT-based program for any time period (including cCBT, web-based/assisted CBT, CBT games, CBT mobile applications, blended cCBT and face-to-face)
- A stated focus on qualitative data documenting the experiences of the participants that allows them to

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express their thoughts, feelings, reflections, both positive and negative feedback, and overall perspectives

- Studies published in English

Exclusion Criteria:

- CBT is delivered only via face-to-face, with no technological component to the CBT delivery
- Solely focussed on specific technology and not the overall experience of the participant(s) using it
- Numerical data that seeks to represent qualitative data

Intervention(s), exposure(s)

Any form of technology-assisted CBT-based program for any time period (including cCBT, web-based/assisted CBT, CBT games, CBT mobile applications, blended cCBT and face-to-face)

Comparator(s)/control

n/a

Context

Main outcome(s)

- Qualitative data reflecting the experiences of participants use of cCBT – this can include: focus groups, workshops, semi-structured interviews.

Additional outcome(s)

None

Data extraction (selection and coding)

Firstly, search results will be imported into Rayyan software (Ouzzani, Hammady, Fedorowicz, & Elmagarmid, 2016). Studies will then be reviewed by title and abstract using the inclusion/exclusion criteria by DM. A second and third researcher (from the TEAM network) will then screen 10% of the overall dataset to ensure inter-rater reliability. Any discrepancies will be addressed between DM and the TEAM researcher - anything unresolved will be forwarded to the expert supervisory panel associated with TEAM.

Risk of bias (quality) assessment

This review will use criteria related to study reporting, validity and reliability strategies, and appropriateness - as detailed by Thomas & Harden (2008). Each study will therefore be critically appraised using the following criteria:

? (i) an explicit account of theoretical framework and/or the inclusion of a literature review which outlined a rationale for the intervention;

? (ii) clearly stated aims and objectives;

? (iii) a clear description of context which includes detail on factors important for interpreting the results;

? (iv) a clear description of the sample;

? (v) a clear description of methodology, including systematic data collection methods; ? (vi) analysis of the data by more than one researcher and

? (vii) the inclusion of sufficient original data to mediate between data and interpretation.

Strategy for data synthesis

As outlined by Thomas & Harden (2008), the qualitative data reported by the selected studies will be subject to:

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- coding 'line-by-line'
- the development of descriptive themes
- the generation of analytical themes that 'go beyond' the primary studies to provide new interpretations and hypotheses

Analysis of subgroups or subsets

None

Contact details for further information

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Organisational affiliation of the review

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Type and method of review

Qualitative synthesis

Anticipated or actual start date

08 January 2018

Anticipated completion date

30 August 2018

Funding sources/sponsors

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Conflicts of interest

Language

English

Country

Ireland

Stage of review

Review Ongoing

Subject index terms status

Subject indexing assigned by CRD

Subject index terms

Child; Cognitive Therapy; Humans; Technology

Date of registration in PROSPERO

25 July 2018

Date of publication of this version

25 July 2018

Details of any existing review of the same topic by the same authors

Stage of review at time of this submission

Stage	Started	Completed
Preliminary searches	Yes	Yes
Piloting of the study selection process	Yes	Yes
Formal screening of search results against eligibility criteria	Yes	No
Data extraction	No	No
Risk of bias (quality) assessment	No	No
Data analysis	No	No

Versions

25 July 2018

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